

A GEOLOGICAL MAP OF THE SOUTH POLE-AITKEN BASIN REGION. C. M. Poehler¹, C. H. van der Bogert¹, H. Hiesinger¹, M. Ivanov² and J.W. Head³, ¹Institut für Planetologie, Westfälische Wilhelms-Universität, Wilhelm-Klemm-Str. 10, 48149, Münster, Germany, c.poeehler@uni-muenster.de, ²Vernadsky Inst., RAS, Russia, ³Department of Earth, Environmental and Planetary Sciences, Brown University, Providence, RI 02912 USA.

Introduction: The South Pole-Aitken (SPA) basin is located on the lunar farside, centered at $\sim 53^\circ$ S, 191° E, and is the largest observable basin on the Moon [1-5]. Several locations within the SPA basin and in particular the South Pole region are targets for ongoing and future robotic and human missions [e.g., 6–10]. The area potentially includes exposed mantle material [14, 15], sources of volatiles (e.g., pyroclastic deposits [11]), and permanently shadowed regions that may harbor ice or other volatiles [12]. With the SPA basin being the oldest lunar basin, the timing of its formation gives valuable information on the formation and evolution of the lunar crust [11,13]. For such missions, detailed studies of the geological history and setting of the region are necessary. Here, we provide a geologic map (1:500k) of the SPA basin region, including the South Pole region and parts of the Orientale basin. An extension of a map of the Apollo basin region [13], our map provides a comprehensive overview of the geology in the region.

Methods: For large-scale mapping, we used the Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter (LRO) Wide-Angle Camera (WAC) basemap (100 m/pixel). To look at smaller areas and to identify specific features, we then also used Narrow Angle Camera (NAC; 0.5 m/pixel) [14] and Kaguya (10 m/pixel) data. Spectral information was taken from Clementine [15], M³ [16], and Kaguya MI [17] data. We determined the topographic features using Lunar Orbiter Laser Altimeter (LOLA)/Kaguya merged digital elevation models with a resolution of 59 m/pixel [18] where available. For higher latitudes we used LOLA digital elevation products [19, 20]. At the poles we mitigate the effect of low solar illumination angles, which cause significant shadows, by producing hillshade maps with various illumination conditions. We worked according to PLANMAP mapping standards [21], an extension of USGS standards [22].

With the available data we identified different units and features based on their morphological appearance, albedo contrasts and, if applicable, spectral signal. We then established a relative stratigraphy for these units using morphological and stratigraphic evidence. Next, we performed crater size-frequency distribution (CSFD) measurements and determined absolute model ages (AMAs) using the production and chronology functions of [23] to put constraints on the chronology. CSFD measurements were made using CraterTools [24]

in ArcGIS, and fit with Craterstats [25]. [23, 26] give detailed descriptions of the technique.

Geology: In this map, we cover the full extent of the SPA basin. We were able to identify the rim of SPA basin, which presents itself best in the elevation data. In the NE part of SPA basin the rim is preserved as a two ring structure. While in most of the other segments of the rim, the rim itself is covered by younger geologic units.

The whole area is covered in small, sharp-rim craters. Most of these craters are likely linked to the formation of Orientale basin to the E of SPA. As the formation of Orientale basin had a significant effect on SPA basin, we included a large part of Orientale basin in our mapping area.

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References: [1] Stuart-Alexander (1978) USGS Map I-1047. [2] Spudis et al. (1994) *Science* 266, 1835-1839. [3] Hiesinger and Head (2004) *PLPSC* 35, 1164. [4] Shevchenko et al. (2007) *Solar Sys Res* 41, 447-462. [5] Garrick-Bethell and Zuber (2009) *Icarus* 204, 399-408. [6] Flahaut et al. (2020) *PSS* 180, 104750. [7] Steenstra et al. (2016) *Adv Space Res* 58, 1050–1065. [8] Allender et al. (2018) *Adv Space Res* 63, 692–727. [9] Hiesinger et al. (2019) *LPSC* 50, 1327. [10] Huang et al. (2018) *JGR* 123, 1684 – 1700. [11] Wilhelms (1987) *USGS SP-1348*, 302. [12] Nozette et al. (2001) *JGR* 106, 23253– 23266. [13] Ivanov et al. (2018) *JGR* 123, 2585–2612. [14] Robinson et al. (2010) *Space Sci Rev* 150, 81–124. [15] Pieters et al. (1994) *Science* 266, 1844–1848. [16] Isaacson et al. (2013) *JGR* 118, 369–381. [17] Ohtake et al (2013) *Icarus* 226, 364–374. [18] Barker et al. (2016) *Icarus* 273, 346-355. [19] Smith et al. (2010) *Icarus* 283, 70-91. [20] Smith et al. (2010) *GRL* 37, L18204. [21] wiki.planmap.eu/display/public/D2.1-public. [22] FGDC (2006) FGDC-STD-013-2016. [23] Neukum et al. (2001) *Space Sci Rev* 96, 55–86. [24] Kneissl et al. (2011) *PSS* 59, 1243–1254. [25] Michael and Neukum (2010) *EPSL* 294, 223–229. [26] Hiesinger et al. (2000) *JGR* 105, 29239–29276.